

**THE AFRICAN UNION'S ENVIRONMENTAL YEAR-IN-REVIEW:
THE PROGRESSIVE DEVELOPMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL LAW**

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(1) INTRODUCTION

This year's report draws attention on the recent developments of environmental and sustainable development issues that the African Union main organs, the Assembly of African Union and the Executive Council, as well as technical organs, the Specialized Technical Committees, have dealt with.

(2) THE ASSEMBLY OF AFRICAN UNION

The Assembly of African Union held on 10-11 February 2019, at Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, its Thirty-Second Ordinary Session. During the session, the Assembly discussed several matters.

(A) Trade and Environment

First, the Assembly decided on the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) (Doc. Assembly/AU/4(XXXII)). In this regard, the decision invoked its own decision (Assembly/AU/Dec.647(XX-IX)), acceded at the 29th Ordinary Session of the Assembly held in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, in July 2017.

Under the terms of the decision, the Assembly addressed the modalities for trade in services negotiations, including modalities for tariff negotiations with 90%, as the level of ambition. Further, the decision approved two important documents, namely the Guidelines for Development of Schedules of Specific Commitments and Regulatory

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Cooperation Framework for Trade in Services and the new Roadmap for finalization of AfCFTA Negotiations with a new deadline of June 2020. In fact, the Assembly determined that it should hold an Extra-Ordinary Summit in July 2019, and acknowledged the deposit of instruments of ratification of the AfCFTA and its Protocols, by fifteen (15) countries, especially Chad, Cote d'Ivoire, Congo, Djibouti, Eswatini, Ghana, Guinea, Kenya, Mali, Mauritania, Namibia, Niger, Rwanda, South Africa, Uganda. Those protocols include the Protocol on Trade in Services recognizing sustainable development and environmental protection as legitimate objectives in the implementation of the AfCFTA.

Second, the Assembly made the decision on Post-2020 Partnership with the European Union (Doc. Assembly/AU/5(XXXII)). Accordingly, it acknowledged the Report of the Chairperson of the Commission entitled, "Towards an Enhanced Continent-to-Continent Partnership with the European Union Post 2020," and advised the Chairperson of the Commission to further the implementation of any decision heeding the Post Cotonou Negotiations, and emphasizing the necessity of an African unique voice in the various platforms and fora of partnership with the European Union.

With due regard to the outcomes of the 1st African Union – European Union Ministerial Follow-Up Meeting, held in Brussels from 21 to 22 January 2019, the Assembly demanded for a "cohesion between the Post-Cotonou Agreement and the Post-2020 Continent-to-Continent Partnership, in order to reflect the continental priorities, as articulated in Agenda 2063 and other related instruments, to be consistent in both tracks." Subsequently, it committed the Chairperson of the Commission to report on the implementation of this decision to its 33rd Ordinary Session intended to be held in February 2020.

(B) Climate Change

The Assembly also addressed the climate change issue. By a decision on the Katowice Climate Conference (UNFCCC COP 24) and Africa's Engagements at the Global Climate Change Conference at COP25/CMP15 (Doc.Assembly/AU/10(XXXII)), it praised and

adopted the report submitted by the President of Gabon, on the Coordinator of the Committee of the African Heads of State and Government on Climate Change (CAHOSCC), on the outcomes of the 24th Conference of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the 14th Meeting of the Parties serving as the Conference of the Parties to Its Kyoto Protocol (COP 24/CMP14), and the Conference of the Parties serving as the Meeting of the Parties to the Paris Agreement (CMA1.3).

Then, it extended its expression of approval to the successful operationalisation of three regional climate commissions: the Climate Commission for the Congo Basin and its Blue Fund, the Climate Commission for the Sahel Region, and the Climate Commission for Island States and ocean economies.

First and foremost, it is appropriate to underline that the decision highlighted the African commitment to fully implement the UNFCCC, and “the Paris Agreement in line with the Principles of common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities”, such a consideration led to the fact the Assembly strengthened its determination to be involved in the “multilateral approach of addressing the global challenge of climate change, through the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change”, and supported “Africa’s commitment to implement the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement, in the best interest of African countries, which are particularly vulnerable to climate change and already adversely affected by the impacts of this phenomenon, while ensuring that African countries are accorded policy space needed to achieve sustainable development.”

The decision further argued the urgency and the necessity for parties to the Paris Agreement to “recognize the special circumstances and needs of African countries”, and openly fostered the pursuit of consultations in order to reach a decision in that regard, by the 25th session of the Conference of the Parties, scheduled to be held in Santiago, Chile, from 2 to 13 December 2019.

The decision encouraged:

“Developed countries to continue to scale up mobilized climate finance towards achieving the 2020 finance goal,

through private and public funds, to deliver on the US\$100 billion annually building on the needs of developing countries and enhancing the country ownership of developing countries, and further enhance the provisions of predictable and sustainable finance building on the floor of the 100 billion USD annually.” (para. 10.)

Then, the Assembly underscored the necessary partnership, including the Commission, Pan African institutions, and Climate Commissions, with Africa Adaptation Initiative (AAI), to underway the achievement of programmes on climate impacts on Africa’s economies and ecosystems, likely to support the proposition of an adequate policy and interventions related to guide African States’ climate response.

In support of the aforesaid, it invited the Commission to organize an African Summit on Climate Change in 2020, prior to COP26, as a means of underlining the year 2020 as critical in the global climate change timeframe.

(C) Sustainable Development and Forced Displacement

The Assembly reached the decision on Revitalising and Operationalising the African Union Policy on Post-Conflict Reconstruction and Development: Practical Policy Options and Adaptative Measures for Sustainable Displacement Challenges in Africa. Pursuant to the proposal of the Arab Republic of Egypt to foster a process of revitalising and operationalising the AU Policy on Post-Conflict Reconstruction and Development (PCRD), which aims at arranging in the straight line with the evolving international discourse on peace building and sustaining peace.

Accordingly, the Assembly requested the Commission to report on further developments of the specific issue of forced displacement in Africa during its 35th Ordinary Session of the Executive Council planned to be held in Niamey, Niger, in July 2019. At this point, it encouraged the Commission to work on practical policy options and adaptive measures likely to approach and seize from its root causes the protracted challenges of forced displacement in Africa, and to

support a dynamic perspective of effective sustainable solutions.

(D) Inter-African Migrations

Reminiscing its decision in July 2018 (Assembly/AU/Dec.695 (XXXII)), adopted at the 31st Ordinary Session held in Nouakchott, Mauritania, which set the scope of the Establishment of the African Migration Observatory (AMO) in the Kingdom of Morocco, the Assembly emphasised the adoption of the Global Compact on Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration (GCM), adopted by the Intergovernmental Conference, on 10-11 December 2018, at Marrakech, the Kingdom of Morocco.

Moreover, it lined the tremendous, mostly operational, role the observatory will be able to assume on this specific issue, and praised the obvious efforts undertaken by the Commission in the process of operationalisation of the African Migration Observatory. The AMO will help to centralise the collection, exchange, analysis, and sharing of data on internal migration with a view to efficiently address migration challenges.

Subsequently, the Assembly demanded for a report to the Commission on the operationalization of the AMO at its Ordinary Session in February 2020. Similarly, it urged the Commission to “expedite the elaboration of the legal, structural and financial implications, as well as the statute establishing the African Migration Observatory for consideration and adoption by the relevant AU policy organs by February 2020.”

(E) Health and Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)

Besides the African Migration Observatory, the issue of migration arose in the shape of the Declaration on Addressing Social Determinants of Health in Africa: Adoption of Health in all Policies Approach. Heads of State and Government of the African Union showed awareness on the interrelationship between the environment and health, particularly in the context of the Sustainable Development Goals.

In fact, the declaration obviously accentuated the issue of the

healthy population is a “driver for sustainable, equitable, and inclusive economic growth”, in the sense that it is envisaged in the inclusive frame of Sustainable Development Goals.

Henceforth, the declaration recalled that:

“Social Determinants of Health is the responsibility of all governments in order to assure adequate, healthy and sustainable environments in homes, schools, workplaces, and communities for the health of their populations and that equity in health is an expression of social justice.”

Thereupon, the declaration contains the commitment to promote the reform or to improve the extent, the value and the quality of the health sector in the African countries, specifically through the integration of the health in all public policies. Then, such a situation will allow the development of a new approach based on the achievement of universal health coverage. It appears that health and health equity as referred to in the declaration are political priorities in every public policy, then states must build effective structures, implement processes and invest necessary resources in order to reach the afore-said goal.

It also follows from this that good practices on the effectiveness of the health system could be documented and evidenced, thereafter the regional and global cooperation could be proved itself valuable.

(F) Towards Durable Solutions to Forced Displacement

The forced displacement within African states was a core topic, with regard to its nature and importance, in the 32nd Ordinary Session of the Assembly. It led to the adoption Declaration on the African Union Theme of the Year 2019, entitled: “The Year of Refugees, Returnees and Internally Displaced Persons: Towards Durable Solutions to Forced Displacement in Africa.” The Heads of States and Governments of the African Union expressed their commitment to endeavour the achievement of goals of “Agenda 2063 - The Africa We Want.”

In this regard, they pledged indeed to deal with the matter of forced displacement and provide durable solutions to humanitarian crises and forced displacement in Africa. Needless to say, that the year 2019 coincides with the 50th anniversary of the adoption of the 1969 Organization of African Unity Convention Governing the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa (OAU Refugee Convention), in addition to the 10th anniversary of the adoption of the 2009 AU Convention for the Protection and Assistance of Internally Displaced Persons in Africa (Kampala Convention). It gave therefore the opportunity to the African leaders to launch the Year of Refugees, Returnees and Internally Displaced Persons in Africa.

As a result, the declaration asserted the significance of adopting “(...) preventive measures towards durable solutions to forced displacement through early warning, early response, early recovery, disaster risk reduction measures, timely humanitarian action, compliance with human rights and humanitarian law and greater participation of the affected population, including host communities, paying particular attention to women, children, young people, people with disabilities and the elderly.”

The Heads of States and Governments of the African Union, therefore, considered that there was a specific necessity to insist in this regard on the link between displacement and peace and security, setting such a link as an essential basis susceptible to sustain durable solutions.

(G) Natural Disasters and Climate Change

The declaration entitled “The Year of Refugees, Returnees and Internally Displaced Persons: Towards Durable Solutions to Forced Displacement in Africa”, drew attention to the connection between natural disasters and climate change and their common impacts. It expressly acknowledged that natural disasters and climate change are likely to “exacerbate existing violent conflict, threaten access to vital resources and disproportionately affect the most vulnerable and result in displacement.”

Consequently, the declaration urged Member States of African Union to strengthen measures to address the effects of climate

change, alongside with environmental degradation and natural disasters, stressing the specific case of conflict-affected areas. It follows from the foregoing that the Commission should provide with a substantive support to Member States, such as helping them to “draw examples of good practices across the continent and identify resources, mechanisms and forward-looking strategies, backed by national, regional, continental and global political commitments to prevent and mitigate the negative impact and consequences of such trends.”

(3) THE EXECUTIVE COUNCIL

On 07-08 February 2019, the Executive Council met at its Thirty-Fourth Ordinary Session at Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, where it approved a set of four important documents prepared, on 08-12 January 2019, by the 2nd ordinary session of the Specialized Technical Committee (STC) on Trade, Industry and Minerals, held at Addis Ababa, Ethiopia (Doc. EX.CL/1111(XXXIV)).

At the outset, the Executive Council adopted four policy documents:

- i) the African Union Small Medium Enterprise (SME) Strategy;
- ii) the Geological and Minerals Information Systems (GMIS) Strategy;
- iii) the African Minerals Governance Framework (AMGF);
- iv) the Africa Mining Vision Private Sector Compact.

Thereafter, the Executive Council heeded the Concept Note on the Theme of the Year 2019: “Refugees, Returnees and Internally Displaced Persons: Towards Durable Solutions to Forced displacement in Africa” (Doc. EX.CL/1112(XXXIV)). After stating the importance of the issue of forced displacements in the context of African states, the Concept Note asserted the necessity of its adequate implementation. In this regard, the Executive Council requested the Commission to report to the 36th Ordinary Session of the Executive Council in February 2020, the necessary measures taken in this spe-

cific frame.

(4) THE AFRICAN UNION SPECIALIZED TECHNICAL COMMITTEE (STC)
ON TRADE, INDUSTRY AND MINERALS

On 11-12 January 2019, the Second Meeting of the African Union Specialized Technical Committee on Trade, Industry and Minerals (Doc: AU/DTI/STC-TIM/MIN/Final/Rpt.) at Ministerial level was held in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. The meeting addressed issues related to the elaboration of continental strategies, including the commodity, small and medium enterprises and trade facilitation strategies. In fact, the meeting welcomed various technical reports considered critical for the implementation of the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA). The STC did not specifically devote time to sustainable development matters.

(5) THE AFRICAN UNION SPECIALIZED TECHNICAL COMMITTEE (STC)
ON TRANSPORT, TRANSCONTINENTAL AND INTERREGIONAL INFRASTRUC-
TURE, ENERGY AND TOURISM

(A) Declaration of the STC on Electricity Smart Infrastructure in
Africa

On 14-18 April 2019, the Second Ordinary Session of the African Union Specialized Technical Committee on Transport, Transcontinental and Interregional Infrastructure, Energy and Tourism (STC-TTIIET/MIN/Draft/Decl.(II)Rev.4) took place in Cairo, Egypt. Discussing the topic of developing smart infrastructure to boost Africa's continental transformation and integration, the STC drafted the Declaration of the Second Specialized Technical Committee on Transport, Transcontinental and Interregional Infrastructure, Energy and Tourism.

As a matter of fact, the declaration urged the African Union Commission to operationalise the Electricity Market in Africa, by means of mobilizing indispensable resources and implementing programmes on small hydropower development, solar energy development, and Renewable Energy in African Island States (REAIS).

Then, it encouraged the “AUDA-NEPAD in collaboration with the AUC, AfDB, UNECA and other regional organisations to develop a continental transmission master plan and mini-grid development plan.”

In the light of the urgency, the STC drew a clear line on the necessity of relying on AFREC/AUC, the AfDB and any relevant regional and continental organizations, in order to assemble the necessary financial and technical resources able to carry on to implement the project on “African Energy Information System, Energy Efficiency Indicator Database and AFREC new Strategy” and the New Deal on Energy for Africa.

Thus, the STC chose to call upon Member States and Regional Economic Communities to consolidate inter-African and continental cooperation in the infrastructure sectors, but mostly, inter alia, to:

- (...) a. mainstream climate change into infrastructure planning and implementation;
- b. formulate harmonized policies and regulations for infrastructure development promoting the use of local content and industrial integration to create local jobs particularly for the youth and women;
- c. speed up signing and/or ratification of pending legal instruments related to infrastructure, notably Maritime Charter, YD, SAATM, AFREC Convention and Road Safety Charter;
- d. address the challenges (safety; infrastructures; regulations) of the maritime and inland water transport;
- e. support the operationalisation of the African electricity market;
- f. develop national and regional tourism strategies to speed up the establishment of Brand Africa.

Finally, it demanded to the Commission to set forth the Declaration on the table of the African Union Policy Organs for consideration and adoption during the meeting, on 17 April 2019, in Cairo, Egypt.

(B) Report of the Ministers' Meeting on Electricity Infrastructure in Africa

On 16-17 April 2019, the Second Ordinary Session of the African Union Specialized Technical Committee on Transport, Trans-continental and Interregional Infrastructure, Energy and Tourism (STC-TTIIET/Min/Final/Rpt(II)) was held in Cairo, Egypt. The minister's meeting focused on the topic of developing smart infrastructure to boost Africa's continental transformation and integration, before concluding its work on the report. Hence, the report devoted further developments on the overall issue of energy in Africa.

(6) THE PATHWAY TO ENERGY TRANSITION

The STC addressed first the issue of Implementation Status of the Plans of Action of the STC-TTIIET – Energy (2017-2019). On this matter, having heard the observations and conclusions presented by the representative of African Union Commission, the STC made two specific recommendations:

- i. Uncompleted activities should be carried forward to the Action Plan of 2019-2021 in addition to new activities;
- ii. The AUC and partners should enhance coordination and monitoring of the implementation of Action Plan.”

Therefore, the STC dealt with the African Union Commission Initiative on Harmonised Continental Regulatory Framework in the Electricity Sector. After underlining the progress made in its implementation, the AUDA-NEPAD submitted a draft of a plan aimed at developing the Continental Transmission Master Plan based power pools' master plans. Indeed, a steering structure of administrative and technical support was proposed for the Continental Transmission Master Plan.

Subsequently, the STC adopted the “Guidelines and Monitoring Plan for Continental Transmission Tariff Methodology” to support the implementation of the “Harmonised Regulatory Framework for the Electricity Market in Africa”, as well as the “Guidelines for

Minimum Energy Performances Standards (MEPS) and Energy Labelling.” Also, it requested to AUDA-NEPAD to “develop the Continental Transmission Network Master Plan based on the power pools strategic plans”, and “ (...) assist Member States with least energy access to develop and implement mini-grid projects for the empowerment of the rural communities and the provision of the required services in health, tourism, education and access to knowledge and information sources beside the development of the commercial and production activities.”

In addition, the STC adopted the African the Bioenergy Development Strategy and Investment Plan for the Eastern and Central Africa Regions, while it encouraged the African Union Commission to work on strategies applicable to the other regions. It carried on by incentivising the Regional Economic Communities and their relevant institutions, notably the Regional Centres for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency to adopt and implement the Regional Bioenergy Development Strategies and Investment Plans developed. Also, the STC requested AUDA-NEPAD to assist Member States in mapping their bioenergy resources and identifying bioenergy projects to focus on.

With regard to the importance of a new continental energy mix, the STC approved also the Africa Renewable Energy Initiative (AREI), as an enabler for the amelioration of the access to energy services and migration towards low-carbon development. It is argued that the AREI will support actions on increasing public and private partnerships likely to fund new energy infrastructures. In that case, the STC recommended that the “AREI Independent Delivery Unit (IDU) should facilitate training of national actors and implement accompanying measures to achieve a maximum amount of renewable energy projects in Member States, regions and the continent as a whole, during/following regional meetings (one per region).”

In addition, the IDU should play a specific role of promoting knowledge transfer and good practice sharing in the field of renewable energy research.

Having further to rule the matter at stake of geothermal resources, in the circumstances of a large-scale debate, the topic appeared to be urgent to some extent. The STC coped with that as a matter of

high importance in the context of the Regional Geothermal Program and Geothermal Risk Mitigation Facility (GRMF) Operationalization. In fact, it advised that the African Union Commission should maintain its policy of sensitisation consultations with the Ministries of Energy of GRMF. Once again, the policy should foster the acquisition of “Power Purchase Agreements, Implementation Agreements and Licences by geothermal developers for the smooth development of geothermal resources in GRMF implementing Member States.”

Latterly, the STC discussed the programme to develop Solar Energy and Small Hydropower in Africa and Support for Renewable Energy in African Island States. The proposal aiming to establish the programme was revealed by the African Union Commission representative. Its scope is to “address the problem of low deployment of solar energy and small hydropower in Africa. In addition, a programme to support African Island States to reduce their dependence on fossil fuels and significantly increase use of renewable and climate resilient energy resources in their energy mix was proposed.” Thus, the AREI is expected to cooperate with relevant stakeholders in the implementation of the programme.

(7) THE CROSS-CUTTING INITIATIVES AND PROGRAMMES FOR ENERGY TRANSITION

(A) Clean Energy Corridors in Africa

It should be noted that in order to support the African Union approach of the energy transition, many initiatives are being implemented. The Africa Clean Energy Corridor falls within the framework of such initiatives. Therefore, it is a regional initiative that includes a substantial scaling up of “clean, indigenous and cost-effective renewable power options” and “cross-border trade of renewable power.” Inspired and initiated by the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), the Africa Clean Energy Corridor was originally processed in the region of the Eastern and Southern Africa Power Pools (Africa Clean Energy Corridor/ACEC). In 2016, the initiative was extended to the West Africa Power Pool region, which braced the creation of a regional power market (West Africa Clean Energy Corridor/

WACEC). In these circumstances, the STC urged the Member States, Regional and Continental bodies to incorporate such initiative in their “renewable energy and climate change agendas” and “to support the Continent’s transition to more sustainable, reliable and affordable energy systems.”

In addition, the STC considered that IRENA should play a specific role in fostering energy interconnection projects and widening into the continental energy grids the share of renewable energy. Finally, the STC encouraged the Member States to share in a large scale their experience on renewable energy implementation.

(B) Sustainable Energy for All (SE4ALL)

Having carefully scrutinised diverse considerations on the Clean Energy Corridors and heard arguments presented by the representative, the STC also discussed the initiative on universal access to energy, supported by the Sustainable Energy for All (SE4ALL). In this case, a short presentation was made on necessary actions to undergo with the aim to achieve the Sustainable Development Goal 7 (SDG7).

Given its core position in covering the current issue of access to energy, the Goal 7 is considered as a vehicle for universal access to sustainable energy by 2030, and such an ambition is underpinned by the theme “electricity for all in Africa” which promotes finance for electricity projects.

Then, the STC urged the Commission to consider that:

“SE4ALL should promote integrated approach to energy sector policy and planning that embraces centralized grid-based means as well as decentralized electrification methods for long-term investment plans.”

(C) Africa Energy Information System (AEIS)

It follows from the foregoing that, the STC also carried on the discussion on the Africa Energy Information System (AEIS), by which means the AFREC publishes annually the Africa Energy Database

since 2012, including the energy balance for all African countries. The STC recommended the Commission to continue to support the AFREC in enhancing the AEIS, but also encouraged Regional institutions and Member States to “allocate the required resources to make the AEIS more inclusive and covering more energy data and indicators.”

(D) Bioenergy Programme: Building Capacity for enhancing bioenergy monitoring, reporting and sustainability in African Countries

In fulfilling its duty according to its prominent role, the STC thereupon focused on the Bioenergy Programme. Its purpose is specifically to “improve and enhance the capacity of the African countries to measure/collect and analyse bioenergy data and establish a strong system of continuous monitoring through the implementation of the Sustainability Indicators for Bioenergy (GSI) and related FAO best practices.” In support of that purpose, the STC advised Member States to take a further action with regard to the monitoring and sustainability of bioenergy production and consumption in Africa.

(E) Oil and Gas Programme: Facilities Creation of African Domestic Market for Oil Products and Natural Gas

It is then worth noting that the STC had a take on the new Oil and Gas Programme. In due course, the programme will be entitled to “focus in creating African domestic crude oil and petroleum products and natural gas market in collaboration with African stakeholders mainly crude oil producers, net oil products consumers, current owners of unused and underused refineries and regional and national authorities.” By all means, the STC recommended to support its implementation and demanded to relevant stakeholders to recourse to necessary resources in order to advance the realisation of the programme.

(F) African Energy Efficiency Programme

Having thus considered the African Energy Efficiency Pro-

gramme, to the extent that it appears to be relevant for the African continent, the STC worked on its objective, which is to significantly meet the requirement of final energy demand and reduce the level of pollution emissions across the continent, and finally to facilitate the increase “electricity access, competitiveness, energy security and economic development.”

In this respect, the STC advised the Commission to sustain the implementation and the achievement of the programme and encouraged to promote partnerships susceptible to bring up technical and financial support, including energy efficiency in public and administrative facilities.

(G) African Energy Sector Transition

In light of various considerations, the STC also expressly acknowledged the African Energy Sector Transition Programme. It is expected from the programme to carry out “Deep Decarbonization Pathways (DDP)” in Africa and steer countries toward decarbonisation action-oriented plans in the continent setting aside South Africa. The purpose of the programme is to provide with a comprehensive insight into the transformations of the energy system, which is aspired in the short, medium and long term, with the intention to achieve “intertwined targets in the specific prevailing conditions in Africa.”

Finally, the STC concluded that the Commission should help to implement the programme, look for and initiate relevant partnerships indispensable to support technically and financially its achievement.

(8) THE CROSS-CUTTING PARTNERSHIPS AND ACTORS FOR THE ENERGY TRANSITION

(A) Africa EU Energy Partnership (AEEP)

The Africa-EU Energy Partnership (AEEP) programmes were at the core of the STC agenda on energy transition players and actors. What was accomplished since the last STC was brought to the table, and it appears crucial to look at necessary adjustment to the landscape in the energy sector which has been designed as the result

of the 5th AU-EU Summit of November 2017. Having heard the presentation of the recent developments of the AEEP, the STC encouraged the Commission to concentrate on solid actions relating to the priorities identified between the AU and EU in the framework of the Joint Africa-EU Strategy (JAES).

In this sense, the STC incentivized the Commission to utilize the AEEP as an enabler of the “strategic alliance” with the EU and other international organisations.

(B) African Commission on Nuclear Energy (AFCONE)

In support of the facts and arguments set out above, the STC had heard a presentation with regard to the background and what had been achieved in the frame of the African Commission on Nuclear Energy (AFCONE). However, it appears clearly from the above considerations on energy transition that the STC had shown a specific interest on the urgency to further renewable energy programmes in Africa, and advised Member States to make sure that the nuclear initiatives are rigorously underway in accordance with all stringent requirements of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA).

(C) African Energy Commission (AFREC)

Finally, the STC did refer to the African Energy Commission (AFREC) activities. For this reason, a representative conferred on the “comprehensive background of its activities, new strategy and proposed programmes.” It was drawn to attention that the AFREC is still at work and the further outcome are to come. Then, in order to reflect their real support and commitment to the AFREC, Member States were urged to accelerate the process of ratification of the AFREC Convention.

In the same vein, they amplified the importance to appoint the Executive Board of AFREC in accordance with the provision of article 8 of the Convention and to further the AFREC host agreement.